

FIRST STEPS FROM NATIONAL LITERATURE TO WORLD LITERATURE

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Abstract. *In recent years, the issue of studying world literature, studying it in a comparative manner with Uzbek literature, and teaching the subject of "world literature" as a subject in higher education institutions has become relevant. The issue of introducing the concept of world literature into scientific application and studying it separately as a subject will be studied separately in this article. Because today, like all other spheres of our country that are opening up to the world, this process is also rapidly developing in the field of science and literary studies. In fact, interest in world literature began in the pre-independence period. In particular, Fitrat, Cholpon, and later writers and literary scholars began to introduce world masterpieces and their authors to our people. After that, modern trends and directions began to enter Uzbek literature one after another. In modern literary studies, serious scientific research has begun to be conducted by F. Sulaymonova, M. Kholbekov, U. Jurakulov, D. Kuronov, B. Karimov, U. Hamdamov, and others. This article provides information about these studies.*

Keywords: *world literature, scientific treatises, world literature, methodological approaches, literary studies, scientific relations.*

Introduction.

The emergence of the term world literature was largely influenced by the great German writer Goethe. In one of his conversations with his true disciple and closest friend Johann Peter Eckermann, Goethe says: "As time goes by, I realize that poetry is the property of the heart of all mankind, and therefore it is used everywhere and at all times by thousands of people. For this reason, I am interested in what other peoples are doing, I study it and advise others to do the same.

Nowadays, the concept of international literature does not carry such a deep meaning. The word world literature (weltliterature) opens it up much more, and everyone must do their part to accelerate the development of this era" [Eckermann I.P. Conversations with Goethe. – T.: "Generation of the New Age", 2021. – p. 324.]. Although Eckermann wrote these words of the great German writer in his diaries in 1827, the concept of "world literature" entered literary studies as a term only after 1835, that is, after it was published in the form of a diary. 1990–2000 With the independence of Uzbekistan, a fundamentally new approach was taken to the issues of world literature in the fields of linguistics and literary studies of our country. During this period, not only translated literature, but also the entire problematic of world literature was comprehensively analyzed within the framework of periodical scientific publications, dissertation defenses, and international conferences. Below, the main research directions, methodological approaches, and main scientific results of this foundation are briefly reviewed.

The main part.

It is known that the appeal of the East to the West or the West to the Eastern culture and literature has led to the formation of a cultural process that embodies the spiritual synthesis of the

East and the West. Such a synthesis is considered a characteristic feature of the cultures of all peoples of the world. The unique traditions of cultural and literary relations, the activity in international relations observed in Uzbekistan in recent years require serious attention to comparative literary studies, in particular, to the issues of the theory and practice of mutual relations and influence. In this regard, it is necessary to pay attention to the fact that different points of view have been expressed by specialists about the subject, goals and tasks of comparative literary studies.

Uzbek literature, along with its historical roots and cultural traditions, has always been in the process of change and renewal. Since ancient times, Uzbek writers have reflected the historical, spiritual and cultural values of the people and imprinted artistic ideas in their works.

However, in the 20th century, with the development of the ideas of independence in Uzbekistan, the introduction of various trends and styles of world literature, a new stage began in our literature.

The issue of studying the problems of world literature began in Uzbek literature directly from the Jadid period. In particular, Fitrat, Cholpon and later Oybek, G. Ghulom, and in modern literary studies, F. Sulaymonova, M. Xolbekov, U. Jurakulov, D. Quronov, B. Karimov, U. Hamdamov and others began to conduct serious scientific research. In particular, Abdurauf Fitrat's treatise "Rules of Literature" provides the first information about the emerging types and genres [Abdurauf F. Rules of Literature. – T.: "G'afur G'ulom", 2008. – p. 240.], Cholpon's first scientific treatise "Tagore and Tagore Studies" (1925) can be considered a scientific innovation in the search for new genres. Through this scientific treatise, representatives of Uzbek literature first became acquainted with the writer Tagore. At the end of the treatise, Cholpon expresses the following opinion: "All of Tagore's poems are melodious, and his melodies are folk melodies.

Each of his poems is read by the people with its own melody, he finds melodies for his poems, and also writes notes. We will leave writing about this great man for a longer time until a serious work is published in Uzbek, and this time we will translate one of his poems in a linear way" [<https://n.ziyouz.com/portal-haqida/xarita/matbuot/jadid-matbuoti/abdulhamid-cho-lpon-rizo-tavfiqbek-1924>]. Along with this information, Cholpon also introduces readers to another writer, critic Riza Tavfiqbek, and his critical work entitled "Hamdnoma".

In addition, the great literary critic Oybek, in his monograph "The Creative Path of Abdulla Qodiriy" (1935) and other articles, studied the problems of the development of Uzbek literature of the 20th century, the influence of such figures of Russian literature as Alexander Pushkin, Lev Tolstoy and Maxim Gorky on Uzbek writers at a high scientific and theoretical level. Oybek's articles in Russian are of particular importance in introducing the achievements of classical and modern Uzbek literature to fraternal peoples.

In addition, as a result of G. Ghulam's translation work, many great works of art became known to Uzbek readers. In particular, he translated into Uzbek the poems of Gafur Ghulom Rudakiy's "Complaint of Old Age", Shota Rustaveli's "The Warrior in the Tiger's Skin", the poetic part of Saadi's "Guliston", the ghazals of Jami and Foni, two rubaiyats of Bedil, as well as I. Krylov's fables, an excerpt from A. Griboyedov's "The Plague of Intellect", many poems and poems by Pushkin, poems by T. Shevchenko, A. Tolstoy, A. Fet, A. Maykov, N. Nekrasov, Zhambul and Suleiman Stalsky, A. Surkov, Lokhuti, I. Bekher, V. Mayakovsky, I. Frenkel, L.

Hughes, A. Tvardovsky, M. Tursunzoda, A. Kuleshov, K. Simonov, and songs of dozens of different peoples. Through these works, the writer introduced not only Russian, but also Persian-Tajik and Tatar writers to Uzbek readers. In fact, this very translation field has been our most painful aspect both before and after independence. Because getting acquainted with foreign works in one's own language is a process that, of course, has a significant impact on the scientific process. Also, the development of these translation processes makes a significant contribution to directly determining the place of Uzbek literature in world culture and its future prospects. The development of the translation process shows what place Uzbek literature occupies in global culture and opens up new opportunities for its future.

New styles and artistic ideas have emerged in Uzbek literature through the influence of world literature. For example, movements such as realism and modernism have entered Uzbek literature and their study by literary scholars, including F. Sulaymonova's "East and West", U. Jurakulov's "Limitless Flirt", B. Karimov's "Alphabet of the Soul", U. Hamdamov's "World Literature: Modernism and Postmodernism", deeply reflected the problems of modernism and modern literary studies in the works of writers, as well as social issues. We must admit that world literature has brought new themes to Uzbek literature. Uzbek writers have managed to widely cover themes borrowed from world literature, such as ideas such as freedom, human rights, and social justice in their works. As we have already mentioned, many works of world literature were translated into Uzbek through translators, which strengthened the position of Uzbek literature in the global context. The translation process strengthened cultural exchange and enriched Uzbek literature.

Despite the deep penetration and influence of world literature on Uzbek literature, Uzbek literature has preserved its national traditions and values. Writers were able to reflect the cultural heritage, customs and history of the Uzbek people in their works.

The influence of world literature on Uzbek literature is of great importance not only in the social and artistic spheres, but also in the development of Uzbek culture. This process led to innovations and changes in the work of writers, but at the same time the issue of not losing the national characteristics of Uzbek literature became relevant. During the influence of world literature, attempts were made to integrate Uzbek literature into world culture, which expanded the creative freedom of Uzbek writers. However, with the adoption of global ideas and themes in literature, the need to preserve the unique features and traditions of national literature is evident. The results show that the influence of world literature plays an important role in the development of Uzbek literature, but it is advisable for writers not to forget the cultural heritage of their people. Uzbek literature should continue to strive to maintain and renew its uniqueness, using the influence of world literature in the future.

Conclusion

The influence of world literature on Uzbek literature is of great importance. The study showed that world literary movements, such as realism and modernism, have made a significant contribution to the development of Uzbek literature. Uzbek writers have managed to preserve national values and highlight contemporary issues through themes and ideas borrowed from world literature. Although the influence of world literature has enhanced cultural exchange, the issue of preserving Uzbek national traditions is relevant.

Uzbek literature should strive to integrate with world culture, but it is important not to forget about national identity. In general, Uzbek literature should continue to create new ideas and opportunities, but maintain its originality.

Literature used:

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